

Table S2: Loadings obtained from the Principal Component Analysis on the 19 scaled morphometric variables obtained from the *Teretrurus* samples. Bold values indicate strong loading with correlation > 0.3.

Character	Description	PC1	PC2	PC3
Standard deviation		3.549	1.602	0.987
Proportion of Variance		0.663	0.135	0.051
Cumulative Proportion		0.663	0.798	0.849
Eigen values		12.597	2.564	0.975
HL	Head length	-0.272	0.012	-0.058
HW	Head width	-0.259	0.009	-0.006
RL	Rostral length	-0.175	-0.130	-0.584
ED	Eye diameter	-0.238	-0.157	-0.180
OL	Ocular length	-0.269	-0.065	-0.026
IOD	Inter-orbital distance	-0.261	0.116	-0.027
IND	Inter-nares distance	-0.249	-0.106	-0.125
SL	Snout length	-0.268	0.098	-0.044
FL	Frontal length	-0.255	0.115	-0.029
FW	Frontal width	-0.224	0.257	0.183
PL	Parietal length	-0.263	-0.015	0.080
PW	Parietal width	-0.240	0.045	0.053
IPS	Inter-parietal suture	-0.184	-0.373	0.065
PFL	Prefrontal length	-0.136	0.525	0.057
PFW	Prefrontal width	-0.247	-0.005	0.046
IPFS	Inter-prefrontal suture length	-0.155	0.477	0.165
NL	Nasal length	-0.216	-0.323	0.144
NW	Nasal width	-0.243	-0.108	-0.063
INS	Inter-nasal suture length	-0.112	-0.284	0.706